

Single-arm Interferometric Plasmonic Sensor integrated on a cladded polymeric photonic platform

K. Fotiadis^{1,*}, L. Damakoudi¹, St. Simos¹, E. Chatzianagnostou¹, D. Spasopoulos¹, D. V. Bellas^{1,2}, O. Bhalerao^{3,4}, S. Suckow³, Max Lemme^{3,4}, E. Lidorikis², N. Pleros¹

¹Department of Informatics - Center for Interdisciplinary Research and Innovation, Aristotle University of Thessaloniki, Greece

²Department of Materials Science and Engineering, University of Ioannina, Ioannina, 45110, Greece

³AMO GmbH, Advanced Microelectronic Center Aachen (AMICA), Otto-Blumenthal-Strasse, Aachen, Germany

⁴Chair of Electronic Devices, RWTH Aachen University, Germany

*E-mail: kfotiadi@csd.auth.gr

Abstract: We demonstrate a high-sensitivity single-arm interferometric plasm-photo-photonic refractive index sensor co-integrated for the first time on a cladded SU-8 polymer waveguide platform, reporting a low-complexity and low-cost sensor with an experimental sensitivity of 6069 nm/RIU.

OCIS codes: Plasmonic sensors; Cladding; Photonic integrated circuits; Aluminum; Refractive index; Liquid solutions

1. Introduction

Nowadays, plasm-photo-photonic sensors have attracted the interest of the scientific community because they combine the low-loss characteristics of photonic waveguides (WG) with the higher sensitivity credentials of plasmonic WGs [1,2]. In order to reduce the fabrication cost and turn-around times, photonic WGs based on polymers in combination with CMOS plasmonic materials have been proposed as suitable candidates. However, until now only uncladded polymeric plasm-photo-photonic refractive index sensors have been presented [3,4], posing a great difficulty to their usage in chemical, biological or agrifood applications. Towards this direction, we extend our previous work presented in [3,4] by introducing a cladding layer to protect the utilized SU-8 photonic WG, and we demonstrate a powerful and ultra-sensitive bimodal plasm-photo-photonic sensor that exploits an Aluminum (Al) plasmonic stripe integrated on the cladded polymeric platform as the sensing element. Adding an experimental cladding layer from Allresist GmbH, we achieve protection of the access photonic WGs not only from environmental parameters, such as dust and moisture, but also from mechanical stress during the attachment of microfluidics which is necessary for bio-experiments including the crucial functionalization step. After thorough numerical investigation, the proposed cladded sensor was fabricated and experimentally characterized revealing a bulk refractive index (RI) sensitivity equal to 6069 nm/RIU, a value higher than the sensitivity reported in [2-4]. This value is in very good agreement with the value expected from simulation of 6078 nm/RIU.

2. Sensor layout and Fabrication

The 3D conceptual design of the proposed plasm-photo-photonic bimodal interferometric sensor is depicted in Figure 1(a). The sensor is formed by two access SU-8 photonic WGs cladded with the Allresist material ($n_{\text{Allresist}} = 1.43$) and separated by an Al metal stripe located on top of an appropriately thinner SU-8 WG layer. In this way, two metal/insulator interfaces are formed at the top and bottom surfaces of the metal stripe able to support surface plasmon polariton (SPP) modes. Upon excitation through a transverse magnetic (TM) photonic mode propagating in the input SU-8 WG, the two modes can propagate along the two respective metal surfaces and interfere at the output photonic WG, realizing by this way the single arm interferometer. The top mode is guided at the interface between the Al WG and the surrounding medium and, thus, plays the role of the sensing arm, while the bottom mode is guided between the plasmonic WG and the underlying SU-8 layer, serving as the reference arm. A change in RI value occurring in the liquid sample above the sensing area affects the highly sensitive top plasmonic mode leading to a wavelength shift at the sensor output. The cross-sectional dimensions of the photonic and plasmonic WGs along with the electric field

Figure 1: (a) 3D schematic of the proposed bimodal sensor, (b) and (c) the two supported plasmonic modes at the top and bottom metal surfaces, respectively, cross-sectional geometry of the: (d) input cladded photonic WG and (e) Aluminum plasmonic WG, (f) schematic of the experimental setup, (g) Microscope top-view image of the plasmonic WGs of the fabricated chip, (h) photo from the fabricated chip with a droplet above the plasmonic structure.

Figure 2: (a) Experimental sensor spectral response for 100- μm plasmonic stripe length in air and water condition, (b) Sensor spectral response obtained for the same plasmonic structure when injecting six different liquids with refractive index varying from 1.3322 to 1.3399 achieving sensitivity equal to 6069 nm/RIU, (c) Simulated bimodal spectral response of the 100 μm long sensor with sensitivity equal to 6078 nm/RIU and (d) Linear fit on the resonance shift versus the above changes in RI values for the experimental and simulated measurements.

distribution of the two supported plasmonic modes (the top and the bottom, respectively) are shown in Figure 1(b)-(e). To maximize the Extinction Ratio (ER) at the sensor output and to minimize the overall losses, we implemented a systematic numerical design analysis. This was achieved by optimizing the thickness of the thinner SU-8 layer ($h_{\text{SU}8,2}$) under the Al stripe in combination with the appropriate plasmonic stripe length, aiming at optimal interference conditions between the two plasmonic modes at the interferometer output. After determining the optimum dimensions ($h_{\text{SU}8,2} = 0.9 \mu\text{m}$), the fabrication of the proposed sensor and the experimental characterization were followed. The fabrication processes were performed on standard 6" Silicon wafers bearing a 3 μm thick SiO_2 layer. The top SU-8 waveguide is hard-baked initially, and then an adhesion promoter is manually spin-coated onto the wafer. Following this, the cladding layer, SX AR LWL 2.0, is spin-coated to create a ca. 6 μm thick layer. An edge-bead removal is carried out, succeeded by a soft-bake on hot plates. Subsequently, i-line lithography exposes the layer, followed by a post-exposure bake. Lastly, the cladding layer is developed using Allresist AR 600-546 developer, rinsed in isopropyl alcohol (IPA). For the plasmonic stripe WG, an 80 nm thick Al layer was deposited using an evaporation deposition process. The fabrication process of the bottom SU-8 layer where the Al WG was attached is presented with more details in [3,4]. The final step included dicing of the wafer into 2 cm \times 2 cm chips. Figure 1(g) depicts a scanning electron microscope image of the fabricated plasmo-photonic sensors.

3. Experimental results

The first step in order to evaluate the proposed device as an RI sensor was the optical characterization of the plasmonic structure in air. Towards this direction, Figure 1(f) depicts the experimental setup that was used to perform the measurements. The setup consisted of a tunable laser source that emits light from 1480 nm to 1630 nm. The light was injected through a polarized lensed fiber into the device under test. A single mode fiber connected to an optical power meter was used at the integrated sensor output for measuring the sensor response. The sensor performance in aqueous environment was evaluated by injecting a droplet of water on top of the plasmonic structure, as shown in Figure 1(h). Figure 2(a) presents the obtained spectral response of a sensor with a 100 μm -long plasmonic stripe when operating with just air and with water on top of the plasmonic section, revealing experimental free spectral range (FSR) values of 37.3 nm and 87.9 nm in the air- and water-cladded plasmonic structures, respectively, that are in good agreement with the respective values expected from theory. RI sensing experiments were then carried out by injecting six different liquid solutions with RI values that were ranging between 1.3322 to 1.3399, rinsing the sensing area with distilled water in order to remove any residues between the measurements with the different analytes. Figure 2(b) presents the bimodal spectra when the plasmonic stripe with 100- μm is exposed to distilled water and five solutions, revealing a resonance shift towards shorter wavelengths as the RI of each solution increases. A fast Fourier transform smoothing was applied to the obtained data to better follow the evolution of the sensor dip. Figure 2(c) depicts the corresponding simulation spectra obtained from circuit level simulations of the complete sensor using Ansys Lumerical "INTERCONNECT" photonic integrated circuit simulator. Bulk sensitivity values were calculated by performing least squares linear fits on the wavelength dip shift with the RI change as can be seen in Figure 2(d). Using this method, the experimental sensitivity was found equal to 6069 nm/RIU, which is in very good agreement with the corresponding value of 6078 nm/RIU that was expected from simulation.

4. Conclusion

We demonstrate an ultra-compact bimodal interferometric sensor that is based on a 100 μm long Al metal stripe co-integrated on a cladded SU-8 photonic waveguide platform and exhibits an experimental RI sensitivity equal to 6069 nm/RIU. Adding the protective cladding layer, the sensor is suitable for functionalization and bio-experiments.

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References

- [1] X. Sun et al, Opt. Lett. 42(4), 807-810, (2017)
- [2] E. Chatzianagnostou et al., ACS Photonics. 6(7), 1664-1673 (2019).
- [3] K. Fotiadis et al., CLEO conf, Stu40.4 (2023).
- [4] K. Fotiadis et al, ACS Photonics 10(8), 2580-2588 (2023).